

PRIVILEGES GIVEN TO WOMEN IN ENTRY TO HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON SOCIETY

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Abstract

This article analyzes the privileges granted to certain categories of women in the process of admission to higher educational institutions, particularly the opportunity to study based on recommendation letters. It also examines the impact of these privileges on women's social activity, employment, leadership potential, and their role in society. Using statistical data, practical examples, and existing legal documents, the article evaluates both the positive and negative aspects of the preferential admission policy. Based on the results of the study, conclusions are drawn about the role of this policy in social development.

Keywords

Women, higher education, recommendation letter, privilege, social impact, gender equality, education policy.

The process of admission to higher education institutions should be based on the principles of social justice and equality. However, in some countries, there are preferences for women in higher education institutions, and these preferences are implemented through recommendations. These preferences provided to women not only expand their educational opportunities, but also improve their role in society, social activity and economic status. This policy is aimed, in particular, at ensuring that women have equal opportunities in obtaining education.

However, the impact of preferences implemented through recommendations on society includes several aspects. They can increase women's interest in education, help solve economic and social problems, and also have a positive impact on gender equality. At the same time, the negative aspects of these preferences can also cause some social contradictions, especially on the path to creating equality in society.

The article examines the impact of educational opportunities for women based on recommendations on society, their role in social life, and how this policy will affect the future development of the policy. The study analyzes the impact of preferential policies on changes in various areas, including education, the economy, and social life. In particular, in Uzbekistan, women from needy families are given recommendations to participate in the competition for admission to higher education institutions based on state grants.

The recommendation is provided based on the following criteria:

- women from low-income families;
- girls in need of social protection who are being raised in a single-parent family, that is, whose father or mother or both of them have died;
- women in need of social protection who have lost their spouse and are raising a minor child alone;
- women in needy families with a disabled child;
- daughters of single women raising 2 or more children and living separately from relatives;
- women in needy families where one or both parents are disabled people of group I or II.

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To receive a recommendation, an application is made electronically to the district (city) mahalla and family support departments.

Recommendations for certain categories of women when entering higher education institutions are an important measure aimed at ensuring gender equality in society and supporting women in need of social protection. These recommendations, as mentioned above, are provided to women from low-income families. For such women, obtaining a recommendation expands their opportunities to improve their knowledge and find their place in society. Low-income families are families facing economic difficulties, and preferences in enrolling them in higher education create opportunities for them to achieve social well-being. In addition, as noted, recommendations are also provided for girls in need of social protection who are raised in single-parent families and are not provided for by their parents. Obtaining a recommendation for them increases their interest in learning and helps ensure their independence in the future. This policy is also aimed at supporting women who are raising their children alone. Women who have lost their husbands and are raising their children alone often need additional support. Obtaining a referral letter helps these women to get an education and create better conditions for their children.

Referral letters for women with disabled children are also an important part of social support. Women with disabled children face many social and economic problems along with their children. Creating educational opportunities for them improves not only their own future, but also the future of their children. Single women raising two or more children and living separately from their relatives also have the opportunity to obtain these referral letters. Since such women are carrying the family burden on their shoulders, they seek to strengthen their position in society through education.

Finally, women from needy families, one or both of whose parents are disabled of group I or II, also benefit from this privilege. Their situation requires not only economic, but also psychological support. Supporting such women, providing them with educational opportunities, will help them better support not only themselves, but also their family members. Thus, creating opportunities for access to higher education on the basis of recommendations is an important measure that will help create equality in education for needy women in society, increase their social activity and strengthen their lives in the future. This policy serves to ensure that women have equal rights in society and will allow them to actively participate in the process of social development.

In addition, according to the legislation of Uzbekistan, women with 5 years of work experience are admitted to higher education institutions on the basis of a recommendation letter. By government decree, women with 5 years of work experience in their specialty in a college or technical school diploma are admitted to higher education institutions on a contract basis. In this case, a separate test is held among applicants with a recommendation letter, and only 500 of them with the highest scores can enter higher education institutions.

According to the legislation of Uzbekistan, women with 5 years of work experience are admitted to higher education institutions on the basis of a recommendation letter. This norm is aimed at encouraging women with professional experience and who have proven themselves in their specialty to study. They are provided with the opportunity to study at higher education institutions by obtaining a recommendation letter, which will help them improve their skills and expand their activities in society.

Also, based on a government decision, women with a college or technical school diploma and 5 years of work experience in their specialty will be admitted to higher education institutions on a contract basis. This step is aimed at supporting women with practical experience in the education

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system. Their work experience and practical knowledge will allow them to improve not only theoretical but also practical skills during their education. This, in turn, will increase the economic and social activity of women in society.

In this case, a separate test will be held among applicants with a recommendation letter. 500 women who scored high points in the test will be given the opportunity to enter higher education institutions. This process will allow women who have achieved the best results and tested their capabilities. Conducting tests ensures transparency of the selection and makes it possible to identify applicants who really have the highest knowledge among women.

In general, this policy encourages women to get an education and supports their professional development. This contributes significantly not only to their individual success, but also to the overall development of society. The benefits provided for entering higher education help to strengthen women economically and socially and create new opportunities for them.

In conclusion, the benefits provided to women through recommendations for entering higher education institutions not only expand their educational opportunities, but also serve to ensure gender equality in society and increase the social activity of women. Providing educational opportunities for women from needy families, those whose spouses have died, those raising disabled children, or those in need of other social protection, helps to increase their role and significance in society.

Also, the tests used for admission to higher education for women with 5 years of work experience will pave the way for the development of their professional skills. This policy will increase women's interest in education and encourage them to actively participate in the process of economic and social development. In addition, encouraging women to pursue education through these benefits will contribute not only to their personal development, but also to the socio-economic growth of society. Thus, benefits based on recommendations will expand women's opportunities for higher education and allow them to create better living conditions in the future.

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